

Research on Awareness and Understanding of Green Consumption Behavior of People in Chau Son Ward, Song Cong City, Thai Nguyen Province

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ABSTRACT: The article studies the awareness and green consumption behavior of people in Chau Son ward, Song Cong city, Thai Nguyen province. The author uses the method of information collection, field survey and statistical information processing. The results obtained: people who regularly hear about the concept of green consumption account for the highest proportion of 36.9% of the interviewed population. The proportion of people who think that waste classification and recycling is the highest proportion of 60.8%, showing green consumption behavior. People know about green consumption through various information such as media (TV, newspapers, internet); or through family, friends, acquaintances sharing; propaganda programs of local authorities at meetings or radio broadcasts or people know about green consumption through schools, training courses, seminars. People know about green consumption through media (TV, newspapers, internet) accounts for the highest rate of 64.9% corresponding to 144 households. There needs to be more synchronous solutions to make green consumption behavior more popular.

1. INTRODUCTION

Wasteful consumer purchasing behaviour contributes significantly to environmental degradation. This problem spans multiple sectors, including food, fashion and retail, each with its own challenges and impacts. Household food waste is a significant portion of food waste occurring at the consumer level, particularly in high-income countries, where household food waste accounts for approximately half of total food waste [1][2] Factors such as impulse buying, poor planning and improper storage contribute to this waste [3], [4], [5].

Positive attitude towards the environment significantly influences green purchasing behavior as shown in the study. "Green purchasing behaviour of young Indian consumers: an exploratory study" [6] and "Exploring the drivers of green purchase behaviour: the moderating roles of perceived expensiveness and green scepticism"[7]. At the same time, awareness of environmental issues and the importance of sustainability will promote green consumption. [8], [9] shown in some studies "Factors and mechanisms affecting green consumption in China: A multilevel analysis"[10]

Currently, there is no research on the awareness and understanding of green consumption behavior of people in Chau Son ward, Song Cong city, Thai Nguyen province. Therefore, the author conducted a study on "**Research on awareness and understanding of green consumption behavior of people in Chau Son ward, Song Cong city, Thai Nguyen province**" to see the understanding of people from awareness of green consumption to understanding of green consumption behavior, thereby providing better solutions for people as well as local authorities and departments to increase green consumption responsibility.

2. RESEARCH OBJECTS AND METHODS

2.1. Research objects

The research focuses on awareness and green consumption behavior of Chau Son ward residents

2.2. Research methods

Method of collecting documents:

In this study, the authors collected, compiled and analyzed documents, magazines, books and data related to the research content Investigation, observation and survey methods in the research area:

The author went to Chau Son Ward to collect information related to the research and used a questionnaire for households

Primary information: Determine the number of sample units to be selected according to Slovin

$n = N/(1 + Ne^2)$, Where: n: sample size; N: total number of households in the study area

Total 2350 households, $e = 6,4\%$ So the sample size is 222 votes. (222 households)

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Data processing method, mathematical statistics:

After the investigation, the author entered the data into Excel and processed the data, drawing charts on Excel.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Some concepts

Green consumption is the use of products and services that have minimal negative impacts on the environment, including behaviors such as using renewable energy, recycling, reducing waste, and choosing organic products. This concept emerged in the late 1960s and early 1970s in response to environmental problems caused by industrial development in Western countries [11]

Key features include environmental protection; sustainable development; behavior change specifically green consumption closely linked to environmental protection efforts. It involves making choices that reduce environmental impact and promote sustainability[12] [13]. Sustainable development ensures that resources are available for future generations by minimizing environmental impacts. Behavioural change is the adoption of green consumption which often requires significant changes in consumer lifestyle and behaviour, driven by increased environmental awareness and values [14].

Factors influencing green consumption include environmental awareness, cultural and social factors and economic considerations. Higher environmental awareness among consumers leads to more positive attitudes towards green products and behaviors. Meanwhile, green consumption is influenced by cultural, social, economic and political contexts, which shape individuals' attitudes and behaviors [15][16]. At the same time, the perceived benefits and quality of green products, along with their costs, play an important role in influencing consumer decisions [17].

3.2. Current status of awareness of green consumption of Chau Son ward residents

3.2.1. People's understanding of the concept of green consumption

The group of authors has studied people's understanding of the concept of green consumption, the results are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: People's understanding of the concept of green consumption

Through Figure 1, we can see that the level of awareness of people is divided into many groups with different levels including "never" heard the term and concept of green consumption, "rarely" heard, "occasionally", "regularly" and "always" heard. It can be seen that the group of people with understanding at the level of "Occasionally" has the highest proportion of 82 households, equivalent to 36.9%, the lowest is "Never" is 1 household, with 0.5%. This shows that a large part of the people have a certain awareness of green consumption. In which, the group of people with understanding at the level of "Regularly" with 30.2% is 67 households, lower than the group of "Occasionally" with 6.7% corresponding to 14 households, this reflects a significant proportion of people have good awareness of green consumption.

In addition, the "Rarely" group accounts for 25.7% or 57 households, lower than the "Often" level of 4.5%, showing that there are still some people who have not fully accessed information about green consumption or have not yet realized its importance. Notably, the rate of "Very often" households only accounts for a small portion of 6.8% or 15 households, showing that there are still limitations in making green consumption a common behavior.

In general, this result reflects that although people in the two groups have a certain awareness of green consumption, the level of understanding and application is still uneven.

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3.2.2. People's awareness of green consumption behavior

People's understanding of green consumption behavior is demonstrated through the use of environmentally friendly products; saving natural resources when consuming; limiting the use of plastic products, disposable products; classifying and recycling waste; and some other actions shown in the following figure:

Figure 2: Chart showing people's understanding of green consumption

The authors interviewed 222 people representing 222 households. Based on the data in Chart 2, we can see the difference between green consumption behaviors that people perform at different levels. The behavior with the highest rate is "Classifying and recycling waste", the lowest is "other behavior".

The behavior with the highest rate is "Classifying and recycling waste", with 135 households (60.8%). This shows that people have a certain awareness of waste management, contributing to reducing environmental pollution and taking advantage of recycled resources. The second action is "Saving natural resources when consuming", with 117 households (52.7%). Compared to the action of classifying and recycling waste, this rate is 18 households lower, equivalent to a decrease of 8.1%. This shows that there are still some people who are not really interested in saving resources such as water, electricity and fuel. The third most common behavior is "Using environmentally friendly products", with 106 households (47.7%). Compared to the action of saving resources, this rate is 11 households lower, equivalent to a decrease of 5%. Although there is a certain interest, this rate shows that it is still necessary to strengthen propaganda to encourage people to prioritize the use of recyclable and biodegradable products. "Limit the use of plastic products, disposable products", with 72 households (32.4%). This rate is 34 households lower than the behavior of using environmentally friendly products, equivalent to a decrease of 15.3%. This number is quite low compared to the seriousness of plastic waste pollution, proving that people's awareness of this issue is still not high.

The group with the lowest rate is "other behavior", with only 4 households (1.8%) participating. Compared to the behavior of limiting the use of plastic products, this rate is 68 households lower, equivalent to a decrease of 30.6%. This shows that most people still focus on common behaviors in green consumption instead of having new initiatives or different actions.

In general, people in Chau Son Ward have a fairly good awareness of green consumption, especially in waste classification and resource saving. However, awareness of limiting the use of plastic products and prioritizing environmentally friendly products is still limited. Therefore, there is a need for more propaganda, encouragement and support policies to raise awareness and promote green consumption behavior more synchronously in the community.

3.2.3. Sources of information on green consumption

People know about green consumption through various information such as media (TV, newspapers, internet); or through family, friends, acquaintances sharing; propaganda programs of local authorities at meetings or radio broadcasts or people know about green consumption through schools, training courses, seminars. In addition, there are individuals who learn about green consumption themselves or through some other sources of information. The group of authors interviewed people and obtained the following results:

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Figure 3: Information source for people about green consumption

Through Figure 3, we can see that the source of information provided to people with the highest rate is "Media (TV, newspapers, Internet)", the lowest is "Other".

The source with the highest percentage is "Media (TV, newspapers, Internet)" with 144 households, accounting for 64.9%. This shows that mass media channels play the most important role in providing information on green consumption, possibly due to their popularity, ease of access and ability to transmit information quickly. The source with the lowest percentage is "Other" with 5 households choosing, accounting for 2.3%. This is a small group, including unpopular sources such as: Environmental non-governmental organizations (NGOs), green businesses and brands, community events and spontaneous groups.

The second highest source is "Local government propaganda programs" with 25.2%, equivalent to 56 households. Compared to the highest source, this source is 39.7% lower, equivalent to 58 households. The remaining sources in decreasing order with the respective rates are "Family, friends, acquaintances" with 20.7%, equivalent to 46 households, followed by "Schools, training courses, seminars" with 19.4%, equivalent to 43 households. Next is "Personal experience" with a rate of 8.6%, equivalent to 19 households. Such a low rate is due to the fact that not many people actively learn about green consumption through practical experience.

3.3. Proposed solutions to raise awareness and green consumption behavior in Chau Son Ward, Song Cong City, Thai Nguyen Province

Education and awareness: Raising public awareness of environmental issues and the benefits of green consumption is essential. This can be achieved through education, media campaigns and policy measures. In reality, many people still do not fully understand what green consumption is, the benefits it brings to individuals and communities, as well as the positive impact on the long-term living environment. Therefore, local authorities need to promote communication activities in various forms such as seminars, talks, leaflets, radio, or via social networks, Zalo community groups. The content of the communication should be close, easy to understand, focusing on practical benefits such as health protection, energy saving, and reducing waste treatment costs. When people have correct and complete understanding, they will tend to be more proactive in choosing environmentally friendly products.

Incentives and regulations: The government can promote green consumption by implementing policies that encourage the production and purchase of environmentally friendly products. High prices come from strict production processes, requirements for safe, environmentally friendly materials, and strict inspection costs. Organizing propaganda sessions in residential areas, neighborhood groups, schools, etc. will help people better understand that high prices are due to the quality and value that the product brings, not due to "unreasonably high pricing". When people have empathy and understand correctly, they will be more accepting and tend to choose green products voluntarily, without any hesitation.

Corporate responsibility: Businesses play an important role in developing and marketing green products and applying sustainable practices throughout the supply chain. Ward authorities can act as intermediaries, connecting businesses with consumers through green fairs, weekend markets or product trial programs. At the same time, build feedback channels from people so that businesses can improve products to better suit local needs.

Strengthen the role of the State through practical support policies for green consumption. Policies on tax incentives, subsidies for green products, technical support for small-scale producers, etc. need to be clearly communicated and to the right target. Ward authorities should proactively update information through public bulletin boards, loudspeakers or local media groups. At the same time, organize dialogues and seminars so that people have the opportunity to directly reflect their needs and propose specific policies. When policies are put into practice and people feel the real benefits, they will be more active in changing their consumption behavior towards sustainability.

4. CONCLUSION

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It can be seen that the nature of green consumption is a humane and strategic activity, aiming to protect the environment, save resources and promote green growth. Although consumers sometimes do not clearly perceive the concept of green products, behaviors such as buying energy-saving devices, reusing packaging or choosing organic products to protect health - are still considered specific manifestations of green consumption in real life. Communication about green consumption through the media (TV, newspapers, Internet) is quite effective. Therefore, it is possible to launch more online competitions about green consumption to reach more people.

REFERENCES

- 1) F. Katt and O. Meixner, "Food waste prevention behavior in the context of hedonic and utilitarian shopping value," *J. Clean Prod.*, vol. 273, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.122878.
- 2) V. Stancu, P. Haugaard, and L. Lähteenmäki, "Determinants of consumer food waste behaviour: Two routes to food waste," *Appetite*, vol. 96, pp. 7–17, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.appet.2015.08.025.
- 3) A. Annunziata, F. L. Muca, and A. Mariani, "Preventing Household Food Waste in Italy: A Segmentation of the Population and Suggestions for Action," *Sustain.*, vol. 14, no. 12, 2022, doi: 10.3390/su14127005.
- 4) S. Gaiani, S. Caldeira, V. Adorno, A. Segrè, and M. Vittuari, "Food wasters: Profiling consumers' attitude to waste food in Italy," *Waste Manag.*, vol. 72, pp. 17–24, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.wasman.2017.11.012.
- 5) V. Stancu and L. Lähteenmäki, "Consumer-related antecedents of food provisioning behaviors that promote food waste," *Food Policy*, vol. 108, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.foodpol.2022.102236.
- 6) S. M. F. Uddin and M. N. Khan, "Green Purchasing Behaviour of Young Indian Consumers: An Exploratory Study," *Glob. Bus. Rev.*, vol. 17, no. 6, pp. 1469–1479, 2016, doi: 10.1177/0972150916660440.
- 7) K. Aydın, M. U. Altan, Ş. G. Köse, and E. Ö. Çizer, "Exploring the drivers of green purchase behaviour: the moderating roles of perceived expensiveness and green scepticism," *Int. J. Glob. Warm.*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 49–61, 2024, doi: 10.1504/IJGW.2024.141404.
- 8) J. Shi and Z. Jiang, "Willingness to pay a premium price for green products: does a reference group matter?," *Environ. Dev. Sustain.*, vol. 25, no. 8, pp. 8699–8727, 2023, doi: 10.1007/s10668-022-02419-y.
- 9) L. Cheng, H. Cui, Z. Zhang, M. Yang, and Y. Zhou, "Study on consumers' motivation to buy green food based on meta-analysis," *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.*, vol. 8, 2024, doi: 10.3389/fsufs.2024.1405787.
- 10) Y. Sun, N. Liu, and M. Zhao, "Factors and mechanisms affecting green consumption in China: A multilevel analysis," *J. Clean. Prod.*, vol. 209, pp. 481–493, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.10.241.
- 11) S. S. Withanachchi, "'Green Consumption' beyond mainstream economy: A discourse analysis," *Futur. Food J. Food, Agric. Soc.*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 69–80, 2013.
- 12) T. Bian, "A Review on Green Consumption," in *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 2020. doi: 10.1088/1755-1315/615/1/012029.
- 13) S.-T. Cheng, K.-P. Huang, D.-Y. Lei, and T.-L. Chiang, "EFFECTS OF CONSUMERS' ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS ON THEIR CONFIDENCE IN ENVIRONMENTAL PRODUCT INNOVATION AND PURCHASE INTENTION," *J. Environ. Prot. Ecol.*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 181–187, 2023.
- 14) J. M. M. Lopes, S. Gomes, and T. Trancoso, "Navigating the green maze: insights for businesses on consumer decision-making and the mediating role of their environmental concerns," *Sustain. Accounting, Manag. Policy J.*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 861–883, 2024, doi: 10.1108/SAMPJ-07-2023-0492.
- 15) L. J. Zhou, *Green consumption: An environmental friendly and healthy approach for Chinese consumers*, vol. 694. 2014. doi: 10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMM.694.426.
- 16) S. R. Nair and V. J. Little, "Context, Culture and Green Consumption: A New Framework," *J. Int. Consum. Mark.*, vol. 28, no. 3, pp. 169–184, 2016, doi: 10.1080/08961530.2016.1165025.
- 17) B. Dropulić and Z. Krupka, "Are consumers always greener on the other side of the fence? Factors that influence green purchase intentions – the context of croatian and swedish consumers | Jesu li potrošači uvijek 'zeleniji' s druge strane ograde? čimbenici koji utječu na namjeru "ze," *Market-Trziste*, vol. 32, no. Special Is, pp. 99–113, 2020, doi: 10.22598/mt/2020.32.spec-issue.99.